

Research paper

A novel 7-level SCMLI with selective harmonic elimination via war strategy optimization

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Switched capacitor MLI
Total harmonic distortion
War strategy optimization
Selective harmonic elimination

ABSTRACT

This paper introduces a seven-level switched capacitor multilevel inverter that achieves triple voltage gain while reducing the number of components, employing a single DC source, two switched capacitors, and ten semiconductor switches. The War Strategy Optimization (WSO) algorithm is employed for selective harmonic elimination (SHE), enhancing switching angles with swift convergence and reducing total harmonic distortion (THD) to around 11 %. The inverter features built-in self-voltage balancing with zero voltage and zero current switchings (ZVS/ZCS), eliminating additional balancing circuits and minimizing inrush currents. The test results for 48 V input generates a maximum output voltage of 144 V at 50 Hz, under dynamic load and modulation conditions, validating the robustness of the design. Analysis indicates that the suggested SCMLI features a reduced peak inverse voltage (PIV) and necessitates fewer components, rendering it a more cost-effective option for high-power and renewable energy applications.

1. Introduction

A Multilevel Inverter (MLI) is frequently utilized in renewable energy applications that require improved power quality in output voltage and current. It generates a stepped AC voltage waveform by generating distinct discrete DC voltage levels. Multilevel inverters offer no advantages over conventional two-level inverters by significantly reducing switching losses and can be operated under a wide range of switching frequency. This leads to enhanced efficiency, minimized electromagnetic interference (EMI), improved voltage and current waveforms, and reduced total harmonic distortion [1]. In general, the total harmonic distortion (THD) decreases as the level count is increased. However, as the voltage levels increase, more semiconductor switches are required. Therefore, the benefits of an inverter are challenged by its size, cost, and efficiency in relation to the total components required to generate large

number of voltage levels.

Optimization of power converter architecture to reduce the component count has been the subject of extensive research in recent years. Extensive studies have been carried out to improve the MLI efficiency with fewer components by innovative ways to reduce switches to generate the desired number of voltage levels. The MLI architecture should be meticulously designed for medium and high-voltage applications as they increase the overall system efficiency while ensuring reduced costs and control complexity.

Among various MLI architectures, Switched Capacitor MLI (SCMLIs) are attracting a lot of attention as these are able to produce higher levels in output voltage with fewer power electronic components as compared to other MLI architectures [2]. SCMLIs can generate multiple output voltage levels by utilizing a single DC source and multiple switched capacitors to replace dc voltage sources [3]. SCMLIs have numerous

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2025.105765>

Received 10 April 2025; Received in revised form 30 May 2025; Accepted 11 June 2025

Available online 13 June 2025

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benefits, like a smaller number of DC sources, an inherent ability to boost the output voltage, and improved efficiency. Additionally, most SCMLIs provide intrinsic voltage balancing of capacitors, thereby simplifying control and minimizing the requirement for additional balancing circuits.

Current research mostly centers on developing various SCMLI configurations to generate increased output voltage levels while simultaneously improving element utilization and minimizing total voltage stress (TSV) on the semiconductor switches. In [4], numerous SCMLI topologies for different applications have been reviewed. The authors discussed in [5], a 5L-SCMLI using four switches, one diode, and two capacitors and filter, that make the topology costlier. In [6], a seven-level SCMLI is introduced that achieves a threefold voltage gain using only two capacitors. However, this design exhibits a voltage imbalance, necessitating an additional control strategy. The approach to addressing this issue involves integrating of two boost stages that utilize redundant switching states to provide and stabilize the voltage across the capacitor. The authors demonstrated in [7] a seven-level inverter, which achieves a voltage gain of two by employing two balanced capacitors charged in series each receiving half of the input voltage through an auxiliary charging circuit that incorporates two power diodes. The inherent use of diodes for the charging and discharging processes leads to notable power losses in the circuit. The authors discussed a seven level topology in [8] that employs eight switches and three capacitors, with a DC voltage source responsible for maintaining a constant charge on the inverter's filter capacitors. This configuration demonstrates an efficiency of 96.76 %, with minimal switching losses and an output voltage distortion of 12.23 %. The authors proposed in [9], a seven level SCMLI topology that has twenty four switches and multiples voltage source. The use of multiple sources makes this topology cost ineffective with increased complexity. In [10], the authors proposed a sevenlevel inverter with reduced semiconductor devices with utilizing one DC source.

Selective Harmonic elimination Pulse Width Modulation (SHEPWM) is a control method utilized to improve inverter output quality by selectively removing particular harmonic components [11]. The precise identification of ideal switching angles in SHEPWM enables the eradication of lower-order harmonics, significantly decreasing total harmonic distortion and avoiding costly passive filters. This method is especially beneficial where efficiency and power quality are essential, including renewable energy systems and motor drives [12]. This discussion explores the mathematical foundations of SHEPWM, addresses practical implementation challenges, and assesses its performance in contemporary power conversion systems. SHEPWM is extensively used in low-and high-power applications to reduce power losses. On the other hand, finding the best switching angles is a complex process, which makes it very difficult to achieve high accuracy using SHEPWM. Researchers have suggested a number of approaches to tackle these challenges. These include the following: the Newton-Raphson (NR) iterative method [13], the resultant theory-based approach [14], and meta-heuristic optimization techniques [15,16].

On the basis of the above discussed literatures some prominent research gaps are-

- Existing SCMLI configurations frequently suffer from switched-capacitor voltage imbalance, large component count, diode-induced power losses, and high complexity which raises the overall system cost with reduced efficiency.
- SHEPWM reduces harmonic distortion, yet determining the optimum value of switching angles is challenging for a wide range of modulation index, which results in poor power quality at the load side.
- A lack of study on effectively reducing the inrush current to reduce the overall rating of the semiconductor switches and enable safe operation of the topology.

This study describes an improved SCMLI design that uses fewer

power semiconductor devices to produce a seven-level output voltage. The system offers a triple voltage gain using two switched capacitors, which are charged and discharged from a single DC source. The circuit configuration offers high-quality output voltage when tested under resistive and inductive loads. In addition to this, the inverter is equipped with a self-balancing feature that ensures balanced voltages across the capacitors. This feature eliminates the need to use extra balancing circuits. In addition, the topology is modulated using SHEPWM to reduce dominant harmonics while maintaining reduced switching losses. A War Strategy Optimization Algorithm is used, which has the ability to converge within a few iterations to find the optimal switching angles.

The novelty features of the proposed study are:

- The proposed SCMLI topology can generate seven-level output voltage with ten semiconductor switches and two switched capacitors with a triple voltage gain.
- The inrush current is significantly reduced with the help of soft switching, thereby preventing the need for additional components such as inductors, etc.
- The predominant lower order harmonics are minimized through the use of the WSOA that identifies the optimal switching angles with improved accuracy and convergence.

2. The proposed scmli topology

This section provides a detailed overview of the proposed Switched Capacitor Multilevel Inverter (SCMLI) topology. It outlines the structure, configuration, and operational principles that enable the achieving of higher voltage levels while minimizing harmonics and enhancing reliability. The design integrates switched capacitors to achieve enhanced voltage gain and employs soft-switching techniques for improved operational efficiency.

2.1. Configuration of topology

The suggested inverter topology is divided into four main parts, as shown in Fig. 1. Two half-bridge units and two switching capacitor (SC) modules make up these portions. All of the loads and capacitors receive their power from the DC voltage source, which is indicated by V_{dc} . The switched capacitors unit consists of switches $Q_1, Q_2, Q_3, Q_4, Q_5,$ and Q_6 and capacitors C_1 and C_2 , connected in parallel with the DC source. To further adjust the output voltage polarity, two half-bridge circuits are formed by auxiliary bidirectional switches Q_7, Q_8, Q_9, Q_{10} . These work as polarity conversion half bridges, establishing the output voltage polarity.

2.2. Analysis of switching states

Table I shows the operational switching states of the proposed topology to achieve multiple output voltage levels, both positive and

Fig. 1. Proposed seven-level SCMLI topology.

Table I
Switching States of the Proposed Topology.

State	Output Voltage Level	ON-switches	C ₁	C ₂
1	3V _{dc}	Q ₂ , Q ₄ , Q ₇ , Q ₁₀	D	D
2	2V _{dc}	Q ₁ , Q ₄ , Q ₇ , Q ₁₀	D	-
3	1V _{dc}	Q ₆ , Q ₇ , Q ₁₀	-	-
4	0	Q ₁ , Q ₃ , Q ₅ , Q ₇ , Q ₈	C	C
5	-1V _{dc}	Q ₆ , Q ₈ , Q ₉	-	-
6	-2V _{dc}	Q ₁ , Q ₄ , Q ₈ , Q ₉	D	-
7	-3V _{dc}	Q ₂ , Q ₄ , Q ₈ , Q ₉	D	D

* C: Charging; D: Discharging; '-': No Change.

negative, as multiples of dc source V_{dc}. In the Table I, ‘‘C’’ denotes charging of the capacitor, ‘‘D’’ presents discharging of the capacitors and ‘‘-’’ denotes the no change of the capacitor states.

- State 1, with an output of 3V_{dc}, switches Q₂, Q₄, Q₇ and Q₁₀ are turned on, resulting in the discharge of both capacitors C₁ and C₂.
- State 2 (2V_{dc}), the switches Q₁, Q₄, Q₇ and Q₁₀ are turned on, resulting in the discharge of capacitor C₁ while capacitor C₂ remains charged.
- State 3 (1V_{dc}) operating switches are Q₆, Q₇, and Q₁₀, while maintaining the charge states of both capacitors unchanged.
- State 4 (zero voltage output), the turning on of switches Q₁, Q₃, Q₅, Q₇ and Q₈ leads to the charging of both capacitors and achieves zero voltage/current crossing (ZVC/ZCC) to mitigate the inrush current.
- State 5 (-1V_{dc}), where switches Q₆, Q₈ and Q₉ are turned on without changing capacitor states.
- State 6 (-2V_{dc}), in which switches Q₁, Q₄, Q₈ and Q₉ are engaged, causing the discharge of capacitor C₁ while C₂ remains charged; and
- State 7 (-3V_{dc}), achieved by activating switches Q₂, Q₄, Q₈ and Q₉, leading to the discharge of both capacitors.

The organized switching sequence enables precise control of output voltage levels and capacitor balancing without any external circuit in the proposed topology. Fig. 2 provides the current paths to generate different voltage levels for a complete positive cycle, which is indicated by distinct colors.

2.3. Self-voltage balancing of capacitor and reduction in inrush current

Several multilevel inverter (MLI) topologies lack intrinsic mechanisms to regulate capacitor voltages, often necessitating additional circuitry or complex control strategies to maintain voltage equilibrium. The proposed topology addresses this limitation by incorporating a self-voltage balancing capability. As depicted in Fig. 3, the seven-level output voltage is accompanied by corresponding charging and

Fig. 2. Current path of different states.

discharging profiles. During the zero state, capacitors C₁ and C₂ are connected in parallel with the DC source and charged to V_{dc}. This soft switching minimizes the inrush currents in both capacitors by charging from zero voltage level, thereby achieving ZVS as shown in Fig. 4. Moreover, equal charging intervals for both capacitors inherently balance their voltages, while the distinct charging states contribute to an improved voltage profile during load transients.

2.4. Analysis of capacitor values C₁ and C₂

The proposed MLI integrates a capacitor to provide support for both current and voltage. The voltage levels produced by the MLI are contingent upon the magnitude of the input supply voltage. Furthermore, fluctuations in load current significantly affect the magnitude of the output voltage. Implementing of the MLI at the output stage leads to variations in the capacitor voltage. Moreover, the fluctuation in capacitors to forming voltage level causes the voltage ripple. The size of the capacitor is determined by the longest discharging time.

Capacitor C₁ undergoes discharge from α₂ to α'₂. The decrease in voltage throughout capacitor C₁ can be stated as

$$\Delta v_{c_1} = \frac{\Delta Q_{c_1}}{c_1} = \frac{1}{c_1} \int_{\alpha_2}^{\alpha'_2} i_o dt \quad (1)$$

Q_{c₁} represents the charge released by the capacitor during the discharge period. To determine the optimal value of C₁ for a specified ripple voltage, V_{c₁}, Eq. (1) is used to calculate the discharge time. The interval from α₂ to π - α₂ is provided in Eq. (2). The final expressions for C₁ and C₂ can be derived from Eqs. (3) and (4), respectively.

$$C_1 > \frac{1}{2\pi f \Delta v_{c_1}} \int_{\alpha_2}^{\pi-\alpha_2} i_o \sin(\omega t - \varphi) d(\omega t) \quad (2)$$

$$C_1 > \frac{i_o}{\pi f \Delta v_{c_1}} \cos \alpha_2 \cos \varphi \quad (3)$$

$$C_2 > \frac{i_o}{\pi f \Delta v_{c_2}} \cos \alpha_3 \cos \varphi \quad (4)$$

2.5. Modulation scheme

SHE method is employed to ascertain the switching angles necessary for the proposed inverter. Three switching angles, denoted as α₁, α₂ and α₃ are chosen within the interval of 0 to π/2 radians. The specified angles are critical for the synthesis of a seven-level voltage waveform. The load voltage waveform can be expressed mathematically as follows:

$$f = \min_{\alpha_i} \left\{ \left(100 \frac{(V_{1d} - V_1)}{V_{1d}} \right)^4 + \frac{1}{4} \sum_{h=5,7} \frac{1}{h} \left(100 \frac{V_h}{V_1} \right)^2 \right\} \quad (5)$$

The primary objective of both sections of the SHE fitness function is to minimize 5th and 7th order harmonics, while the first part is concerned with decreasing percentage error in the fundamental voltage amplitude. The minimum value of this function is desired as it provides an exact solution to the SHE problem. The performance of the proposed WSO algorithm to solve SHE exceeds that of traditional and advanced optimization algorithms based on of speed and convergence accuracy and achieves the best accuracy, as low as 1 × 10⁻⁵⁴.

2.5.1. Proposed SHE algorithm

The proposed WSO optimization algorithm is a novel metaheuristic framework derived from military strategies for addressing intricate optimization challenges. As shown in Fig. 5, the algorithm begins by initializing essential parameters, including a soldier strength of 30, the problem’s dimensions, and the respective lower and higher boundaries

Fig. 3. Pattern of Capacitors charge and Discharge.

Fig. 4. Inrush current profile of both capacitors.

of the search space, while establishing key leaders such as the King and the Army Commander (both initialized as zero vectors). Each candidate solution, symbolized by a soldier, is randomly and uniformly distributed within the defined search space, and its effectiveness is quantified as an “attack force.” The soldiers’ fitness is then evaluated, with the highest-performing candidate designated as the King and the second-best as the Commander. During each of the 100 iterations, a probabilistic mechanism controlled by a threshold parameter ($pr = 0.5$)—guides the soldiers to either explore new regions or exploit known good areas by updating their positions accordingly. The algorithm further refines the search by recalculating fitness, sorting candidates, updating positions based on both current and historical performance, and adjusting ranks and weights to reflect their success. Furthermore, soldiers exhibiting the lowest fitness levels are recognized and carefully reassigned to improve search diversity. The interaction between exploration and exploitation, along with ongoing performance assessment and adaptive adjustment, is fundamental to the WSO algorithm’s efficacy in reaching an optimal solution.

2.5.1.1. Comparison of WSO with state-of-the-art SHE algorithm. This analysis examines the exploration and exploitation performance of the Weighted Sum Optimization (WSO) method compared to APSOGA, QBA, QMN, and GWO across 100 iterations using 30 search agents to evaluate the three-dimensional SHE fitness function. A total of 25

simulations were conducted for various modulation index values, and the average fitness outcomes were compared. Fig. 6(a) depicts the correlation between switching angles and modulation index as established by WSO. Table II illustrates that WSO passes through the SHE search space with an improved convergence rate, attaining markedly lower fitness values in the early iterations relative to other methods. The elevated exploration pace of WSO facilitates the quick identification of the preliminary SHE solution. Furthermore, its capacity for exploitation exceeds that of all alternative methods. Fig. 6(b) shows the different values of THD for a wide range of modulation index (MI) from 0.5 to 1.

At a MI of 0.6, WSO swiftly attains the threshold of the original SHE solution within five iterations, but APSOGA, QBA, QMN, and DMOA converge after the eighth iteration. At $M = 0.6$, WSO outperforms the other algorithms, reaching an optimal fitness value of 10^{-41} in under 75 iterations. The WSO algorithm shows fast convergence for $M = 0.7$, finding the initial solution in four iterations and reaching an accuracy of 10^{-44} . WSO outperforms other approaches that show lesser accuracy throughout 25 runs, achieving optimal solutions at $M = 0.8$ and $M = 0.85$, and converging to a maximum accuracy of 10^{-54} .

3. Comparative analysis with state-of-the-art SCMLI topologies

Table III summarizes the evaluated proposed MLI against alternative MLIs having an identical number of levels of voltage and a triple voltage

Fig. 5. Flowchart of proposed WSO algorithm.

Fig. 6. (a) Optimal WSO switching angles for a wide modulation index range (b) THD at 0.5 to 1 modulation index.

gain. The main objective of the given topology is to greatly minimize the number of necessary components while yet producing an output voltage waveform of good quality.

In [21], a seven-level inverter design that utilizes a reduced number of switches demonstrates high inrush currents. This configuration exhibits elevated THD and TSV performance. The authors in [8] suggested a 7-level topology consisting of twelve switches, three capacitors, and twelve gate drivers, resulting in a THD of approximately 24 %. In [22], an SCMLI architecture consisting of nine switches and three capacitors, leading to diminished PIV and TSV, with a THD of around 12.23 %, has been proposed. In comparison to the previous topology, [23] has utilized only ten switches, ten gate drivers, and two capacitors with low PIV,

albeit with a high inrush current. The topology presented in [24] utilizes a greater number of capacitors than similar topologies, as evidenced by the comparative analysis in Table III. In the topology described in [25], a single DC supply is used along with seven power switches, three diodes, two capacitors, and one inductor to create a seven-level SCMLI module. The incorporation of power diodes and inductors into this topology results in an increase in the total component count (TCC), which in turn leads to an increase in cost in comparison to other topologies under consideration. The topology proposed here demonstrates reduced THD, PIV, and TSV by utilizing only ten switches, and fewer gate drivers in comparison to alternative state-of-the-art topologies. The topology minimizes the inrush current generated in capacitors by implementing a

Table II
Evaluation of fitness values across different modulation indices.

Algorithm	Modulation Index (M)							
	0.6		0.7		0.8		0.9	
	I	FV	I	FV	I	FV	I	FV
APSOGA [17]	75	10^{-4}	73	10^{-5}	70	10^{-6}	68	10^{-7}
QBA [18]	70	10^{-4}	68	10^{-6}	65	10^{-4}	63	10^{-5}
QMN [19]	80	10^{-8}	74	10^{-9}	72	10^{-5}	73	10^{-8}
DMOA [20]	20	10^{-38}	30	10^{-42}	50	10^{-52}	51	10^{-52}
Proposed WSO	6	10^{-41}	10	10^{-44}	8	10^{-54}	8	10^{-54}

I = No. of Iterations, FV = Minimum Fitness value.

step charging method during the charging cycle.

4. Experimental results

Fig. 7 shows the lab-scale experimental prototype of the 7-level MLI, which is developed to validate the proposed SHE method. The proposed SCMLI receives its power from four series connected to a 12 V, 80 Ah battery to provide a 48 V, 80 Ah input dc source to SCMLI. A power quality analyzer, a load bank, an ATMEGA32 controller, a digital storage oscilloscope (TDS2024C), and a battery bank make up the 7L-MLI experimental setup. Table IV displays the parameters that have been employed for the experimental investigation.

Table III
Comparison of the Proposed Topology with Prior-Art SCMLI Topologies.

Ref.	MT	N_s	V_{dc}	N_c	N_{gd}	N_l	N_d	THD (%)	PIV	TSV_{pu}	IC
[21]	PWM	8	1	2	8	1	1	17.95	5	20	H
[8]	PSPWM	12	3	3	12	0	0	24	4	33	M
[22]	SVM	9	1	3	9	0	1	12.23	2	20	H
[23]	PD-PWM	10	1	2	10	0	0	16.26	3	14	H
[24]	PODPWM	12	1	4	12	0	0	29.85	2	16	M
[25]	PD-PWM	7	1	2	7	1	3	-	3	16	L
P	SHE	10	1	2	6	0	0	11	3	20	L

N_s =No. of switches, N_d = No. of diodes, N_c = No. of capacitors, N_{gd} = No. of gate drivers, N_l = No. of inductors, N_{dc} = No. of dc sources, THD = Total harmonics distortion, P = Proposed topology, MT = Modulation Technique, PIV = Peak inverse voltage, TSV_{pu} = Total standing voltage per unit.

4.1. Dynamic change in modulation index

The preliminary case study demonstrates that variations in the modulation index lead to a reduction in both voltage and current peaks. At $M = 0.85$, the voltage and the current rms values are measured at 99 V and 1.97 A, respectively. Due to the reduction in $M = 0.8$ the voltage and current rms values are decreased to 91.2 V and 1.82 A, respectively. This case study is performed to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed strategy in response to a dynamic change in the modulation index, which is varied from $M = 0.85$ to 0.8, as depicted in Fig. 8.

4.2. Dynamic change in load condition

In this case study a sudden shift from Load A ($R = 70 \Omega$) to Load B ($R = 100 \Omega$ and $L = 150 \text{ mH}$) is carried out at $M = 0.85$ which leads to a decrease in the RMS value of the load current to 1.3A from 2A as shown in Fig. 9. Moreover, the voltages across capacitors C_1 and C_2 remain balanced at 48 V for sudden change in load condition.

Table IV
Parameters Chosen for Experimental Study.

Electrical Parameter	Value
Input Source (V_{dc})	48 V
Switching frequency	50 Hz
MOSFET (FDB15N50)	500 V, 15A
R-L load	50 Ω –15 mH
Capacitors, C_1, C_2	9000 μF , 5000 μF

Fig. 7. Experimental setup of the proposed 7-level topology.

Fig. 8. Variation from 0.85 to 0.8 in the modulation index.

Fig. 10. Under a dynamic change in frequency from 50 Hz to 100 Hz.

Fig. 9. Variation in load condition from Load A to Load B.

4.3. Variation in switching frequency

Fig. 10 illustrates the effect of change in frequency from 100 Hz to 50 Hz. The voltage across capacitors C_1 and C_2 is maintained at a constant 48 V, ensuring stability within the system. As the switching frequency changes dynamically, the architecture continues to function with a modulation index of $M = 0.85$. Under both switching frequency, the THD remain relatively same and is measured at around 11 %.

5. Conclusion

This paper introduces a new seven-level switched capacitor multi-level inverter (SCMLI) topology that attains a triple voltage gain utilizing a single DC source, two switched capacitors, and ten semiconductor switches. The incorporation of a War Strategy Optimization (WSO) algorithm for selective harmonic elimination facilitates swift convergence

to optimal switching angles, significantly reducing lower-order harmonics and attaining a THD of around 11 %. By applying ZVS/ZCS, the inherent self-voltage balancing may be accomplished during capacitor charging. This lowers inrush currents, thereby avoiding the use of extra circuitry and ensuring that capacitor voltages are kept constant independent of load conditions or modulation indices. Validation investigations show that the system performs well for both resistive and inductive loads for 48 V input and generates a maximum output voltage of 144 V at 50 Hz. The presented design exhibits a reduced number of components and a diminished PIV in comparison to existing SCMLI configurations. This study presents a system designed for applications requiring high power and renewable energy, characterized by its economical, efficient, and scalable attributes.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ankit Singh: Writing – original draft, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Vibhu Jatley:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Peeyush Kala:** Validation, Supervision, Resources. **Jyoti Joshi:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Software. **Nitin Kumar Saxena:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Software, Resources. **Shashank Mishra:** Supervision, Software, Resources. **Pavan Khetrpal:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Supervision, Resources. **Brian Azzopardi:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This work was funded in part by “TRANSITION to Sustainable Future through Training and Education” TRANSIT Project under European Union Grant 101075747 and U.K. Research and Innovation (UKRI), Photovoltaics Reliability Operations and Maintenance Innovative Solutions for Energy Alliance (PROMISE) Project under European Union Grant 101079469; and Robust Optimization Framework for Photovoltaics and Electric Vehicles Integration at Low Voltage Network Project (RoOFPEVs) Project under Xjenza Malta Grant REP-2023-061.

Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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